

CRYOGENIC HYDROGEN STORAGE IN THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITE VESSELS

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HYDROGENISATION GLOBALLY

Portrait of a Hydrogen Tank

- Efficiency currently limited by storage method, i.e. high pressure

P [MPa]	ρ_{H_2} [kg/m ³]	c_g [%]
35-70	30-40	<7

- To **lower pressure-stresses** and **increase storage capacity**, **cryogenic storage** seems like „logical“ progression
 - $\rho_{H_2} \sim 70 \text{ kg/m}^3$
 - $P < 0.5 \text{ MPa}$
 - $T = -253^\circ\text{C} (20 \text{ K})$
- However, permeability and low-temperature properties remain critical to vessel success.

Literature Permeability and Low-temperature Properties

- Various studies since 1961

Permeability

Fibre content [Humpenöder, 1998]

Fibre type [Flanagan et al., 2017]

Polymer (amorphous) chain
[Su et al., 2021]

Crystallinity [Amanat et al., 2011]

Low-temperature Properties

Effect of low temperatures on strength and strain of PPS
[recreated from Yano and Yamaoka, 1995]

Scope of DLR Activities

Achieving complex geometries

Permeability of high-performance thermoplastic composites

Influence of low temperatures

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Lukas Raps
HH:MM
DD.MM.YY

Today's topic

Simon Hümbert
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Manufacturing Hydrogen Storage Vessels

- Winding and infiltration – thermoset state-of-the-art

- In-situ layup – Disruptive thermoplastic technology

→ In-situ

→ In-situ + consolidation

Scope of Permeability Study

- Manufacturing
 - In-situ AFP
 - In-situ AFP + consolidation
- Layup
 - $[0,45,90,-45]_{2s}$
 - $[0]_{12}$
- Prepreg
 - 60%
 - 55%
- Polymer
 - LM-PAEK
 - PPS

PRELIMINARY RESULTS

Preliminary Results – Permeability

- 5 bar ($\sim 5E5$ Pa)
- RT (~ 295 K)

- Fickian/Non-Fickian behaviour

- Time to peak value
 - 25-30 Hr

- Conversion of He to H₂
 - [Humpenöder, 1998]

Preliminary Results – Permeability

- Room temperature measurements as of 19.05.2023

Config	P [$\times 10^{-16}$ mol.m/m ² .Pa.s]			Literature
	QI, normal	QI, thin	UD, normal	
Thermoset reference 60%	0,64	-	-	0,15
CF-LMPAEK 60%, press	0,61	-	-	0,42
CF-LMPAEK 55%, AFP	6,47	-	-	-
CF-LMPAEK 55%, AFP + press	-	-	0,36	-
CF-LMPAEK 60%, AFP + press	-	0,71	-	-

- mol.m/m².Pa.s?...

Preliminary Results – Permeability

- Reference tank:
 - $\sim \Phi 2300$ mm (inner)
 - $L = \sim 1670$ mm (inner)
 - $V_{H_2} = 5.893$ m³
 - $m_{H_2} = 412.5$ kg

- Reference tank:
 - Type-V (no liner)
 - No insulation
 - Single wall

d_{wall} [mm]	$m_{H_2} + m_{tank}^*$ [kg]	c_g [%]
1	437.8	94.2
2	463.1	89.1
3	488.3	84.5
5	538.6	76.6
10	663.6	62.2

*Estimated laminate density = 1600 kg/m³

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Preliminary Results – Permeability

- Room temperature measurements as of 05.05.2023

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- **Still many measurements remaining**
- Interaction with **low temperatures** also crucial

Permeability at Cryogenic Temperatures – Next Step

- New facility
 - $\Phi 100$ mm (test)
 - $d < 5$ mm
 - $5E^{-10}$ Pa.m³/s

Other Ongoing Activities

Achieving complex geometries

Transfer of 3D geometries to 2D samples

Layup planning for different tank geometries and scales

Permeability of high-performance thermoplastic composites

Cryogenic/cycled permeability

Manufacture of cylinder test samples ($\Phi 200\text{mm} \times 400\text{mm}$)

Influence of low temperatures

Liner material investigations

Cryogenic cylinder tests

THANK YOU; QUESTIONS?

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